

Managing Academic Faculty During Wars

Case of e-HRM During the Devastating War on Gaza 2023-2025

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Abstract

This study investigates the critical role of Electronic Human Resource Management (e-HRM) in sustaining higher education operations during wartime, focusing on the Islamic University of Gaza (IUG) as a case study. Amid the devastating 2023-24 war, which destroyed infrastructure and disrupted academic activities, IUG leveraged e-HRM systems to maintain core functions. Using a qualitative case-study approach, the research analyses IUG's adaptive strategies, including cloud-based HR tools, remote collaboration platforms, and digital payroll solutions, while comparing them with resilience models from other conflict zones (e.g., Ukraine, Syria).

Key findings reveal that decentralised digital infrastructure, cybersecurity measures, and trauma-informed HR policies are essential for institutional survival in crises. The study highlights the challenges of implementing e-HRM amid electricity blackouts, internet outages, and staff displacement, while underscoring the need for international support and scalable technological solutions. By bridging theory and crisis response, this paper offers actionable insights for higher education institutions in conflict-affected regions and contributes to broader discussions on organisational resilience and digital transformation in emergencies.

Keywords: e-HRM, War on Gaza, Higher Education, Crisis Management, Islamic University of Gaza, Organisational Resilience.

1.0 Introduction

Modern organisations are of great importance to the human element, especially in facing the challenges and transformations witnessed by the business environment. The human element enjoys flexibility and the ability to adapt to changes, and contributes to generating ideas, rapid learning and improving performance, in the face of crises such as wars, which makes the human resource more valuable in enabling organizations to adapt and balance, and in particular what the Palestinian society faces from the impact of continuous wars and crises, especially in Gaza, which witnessed most devastating war since October 2023 that affected all sectors, including higher education.

This study highlights the importance of e-HRM and remote work as a basic means of continuing work and progress in difficult circumstances, which helps in achieving balance and sustainability in the educational process in light of the war on Gaza. The paper also addresses the ability of higher education institutes as the Islamic University in Gaza to withstand challenges and manage the devastation in human factors. Buheji (2025b)

Through the research paper, we aim to highlight the role of e-HRM during the war on Gaza through its functions and policies. The study concludes with a proposal for implementing electronic management by developing a strategy for the electronic management project, seeking the assistance of consulting bodies to participate in the study and develop plans, and providing the necessary material capabilities to develop electronic networks and information technology, in order to increase interaction between departments and deanships, and with beneficiaries.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Importance of the Focused Agile Human Resources During & After the Wars

Today's modern organisations place great importance on the human element in confronting the various transformations taking place in the business environment, given its flexibility and ability to continuously adapt to various challenges. They rely on human resources to generate ideas, learn quickly, and improve performance by acquiring and utilizing multiple skills and knowledge. This increases the skills that enrich both the organization and the community. Reliance on the human element increases in light of the crises that confront organizations, making human resources more valuable in overcoming difficult circumstances and achieving effective balance in exceptional circumstances (Bousaha and Bossosa, 2023).

Adapting to complex local and global changes has become increasingly difficult, given the serious disasters and crises the world has witnessed in recent years, including wars, particularly in Palestinian society. The brutal war that Gaza faced has resulted in a deterioration of the situation on all levels, thus posing challenges to the education sector. Local organisations, bodies, and institutions have made significant efforts to keep pace

and coexist with these changes by developing orientalist strategies to advance private, governmental, and service work. This is achieved by relying on human resources that exert efforts to achieve goals (Jabbara, 2023, adapted), and information and communication technology, seeking to maintain their performance levels, maintain their activities, and continue their work by relying on remote work using e-HRM schemes (Boussaha and Boussoussa, 2023). It is based on a basic combination of the human element and e-management systems tools.

2.2 Managing University Faculty During the War On Gaza, Comparison With Previous Experience

Managing university faculty during a war, such as the ongoing conflict in Gaza, presents unique challenges compared to previous crises (e.g., wars, pandemics, or economic collapses). Migdad and Buheji (2024)

Universities in Gaza have faced total destruction. Faculty and students are directly exposed to violence, displacement, and death. All the Gaza Strip have gone through severe shortages of electricity, internet, and basic supplies which disrupted academic life and brought it to a halt. Previous war crises in Syria, Yemen, and Vietnam brought damages to the academic institution infrastructures, but were rarely as comprehensive as in Gaza. Even in the recent war of Russia-Ukraine, universities relocated or moved online in certain areas. Buheji (2025b)

Thus, in Gaza, many academic institutions are non-operational; teaching (if possible) happens in makeshift shelters. Online learning is nearly impossible due to power cuts and internet blackouts. Research is on hold, where the faculty focus mainly on survival while living in the continuous displacement or the Tents. Migdad, et al. (2024b)

The survivors of the Gaza faculty members are suffering in their well-being and mental health. Many experience extreme trauma due to loss of family, homes, and colleagues. With no access to psychological support, the crisis is alarming.

In Gaza today, most Palestinian universities lack resources; salaries are unpaid due to funding cuts, while international aid is restricted or blocked. With extremely limited mobility due to the blockade, most of the faculty cannot leave Gaza.

Since brain drain usually occurs post-conflict, if survivors emigrate, Gazan universities are expecting a major challenge in this issue. Besides, Gazans faculty are actually expecting further censorship or persecution for their views or even active community work participation during the war. Migdad and Buheji (2024)

The situation in Gaza, it a bit similar to the situation in north Syria since (2011). The Asad regime created campus destruction, to bring more displacement. However, Syrian

academics had more escape routes through Turkey and Jordan, and many continued their academic life.

If we compare the situation with the academic institutions in Ukraine, universities in certain areas with the conflict, the accessibility to international support helps these institutions to easily relocate. As we compare the management of university faculty during the Gaza War since (2023–present) with Vietnam War (1955–1975), World War II (1939–1945), and the Yugoslav Wars (1991–2001)—reveals both parallels and stark differences in academic survival, and institutional resilience we can see that even the heavy bombing of the cities including Hanoi University in Vietnam, some universities continued under fire. Even in WWII (1939–1945) universities like Warsaw University destroyed (90% of buildings), faculty executed (Nazi purges). Buheji (2025b)

While in Bosnia, even when the University of Sarajevo was under siege, and shelled daily, "Academic resistance" led the faculty to hold secret classes in basements. Buheji (2025a)

In relevance to academic continuity and resistance, similar to Gaza, where classes in tents and hospitals (if at all), Vietnam established which is called 'Guerrilla education' that was conducted in the underground schools in Cu Chi tunnels. In Sarajevo's underground education the professors taught even by candlelight during the siege. Buheji (2025a)

2.3 Necessities of e-HRM System During the Emergencies of Gaza

Gaza has faced unique challenges as a result of the blockade and repeated brutal aggression, which have significantly impacted various sectors, including higher education. This has made e-HRM an urgent necessity to achieve efficiency and sustainability in the workplace. Further research is needed to understand the importance of this approach and its role during the war on Gaza, as well as the role of e-HRM and the most important tools deployed within this framework to achieve balance and flexibility during the war on Gaza.

2.4 Introducing the e-HRM

In this research we define e-HRM as the distinct application of web-based technologies in human resource-related systems, which, along with other organisational changes, will contribute to broad access to human resources information (HRI) and provide numerous opportunities to manage that information. It is a distinct application of web-based technologies in human resource-related systems, which, along with other organisational changes, will contribute to broad access to HRI and provide numerous opportunities to manage that information (Markham & Hopkins, 2006, p. 6). It is also defined as the ability to use and automate information, communications, and modern networks to implement administrative activities electronically via the internet and the organisation's networks. This allows for automated services to be provided anywhere and anytime,

leading to quality, improved performance, standardization of procedures, speed of implementation, cost reduction, and the provision of necessary data and information to achieve organizational goals with minimal time, effort, and cost, and to develop administrative processes (Boubker, 2023, p. 22).

From the previous definitions, it is clear that there is a need for modern technologies for HRM during emergencies and crises, suitable for cases similar to Gaza. Despite differences in scope, there is a focus on access to information, integration with organisational or community changes. Systems or schemes that help to develop practical goals, such as improving performance, reducing costs, and developing operations. Boubker's definition is characterised by its comprehensiveness and relevance to practical reality, especially in environments suffering from wars and crises, living with limited resources, as is the case now in Gaza.

2.5 Modern Tools and Technologies Used in E-HRM

E-HRM relies on a set of modern tools and technologies. With the rapid developments and complexities of work, there has been a growing awareness of the importance of these tools, which in turn help improve efficiency, facilitate operations, and make smart decisions. Among the most important tools and technologies currently used are SAP that bring together the organisation to improve the resources management as per the daily operations, and to connect different departments together through a comprehensive system that help to reduce costs by reducing paperwork, reduce the need for new recruitment, reducing time by providing an easier and faster way to process data, reducing data conversion time from 1-3 days to just hours, improve communication between departments, standardizing procedures and increasing productivity as a result of improved work processes. Thus, it helps to create a unified database, making it easier for employees to move between different sectors and speeding up transactions. Khoualdi and Basahel (2014).

The other comprehensive e-HRM system is Oracle, which includes features that include core HR processes, talent management, workforce management, and advanced analytics, This system is an effective platform for meeting the diverse needs of employees (Khair et al. 2024). It is an integrated suite of software designed to support and improve various aspects of human resources management. Thanks to its cloud-based design, real-time data access is available, enabling a more flexible and responsive approach to human resources management. Among its most important modules are the payroll, benefits administration, employee records, and regulatory compliance. The HR data is stored in a central repository, ensuring data accuracy and ease of access. The Oracle also include a talent management module that focuses on career development, succession planning, performance management, and recruitment, with a special focus on performance. This module helps organisations align employee aspirations with organisational goals, identify and nurture high-potential talent, and develop individual development plans.

The learning management module in Oracle provides tools for designing, delivering, and monitoring employee training and development programs. It supports the delivery of personalised learning experiences and ensures that employees possess the knowledge and skills necessary to succeed in their jobs. Besides the previous module, Oracle have included a workforce management module that focuses on employee scheduling, attendance and time tracking, and helps organisations optimise human resource allocation and ensure compliance with labor laws.

Oracle Human Capital Management (HCM) module features powerful analytical capabilities that enable organizations to gain insights into employee engagement, performance, and other vital data. By analyzing data from multiple sources, it is possible to identify trends, measure the effectiveness of engagement initiatives, and make data-driven decisions.

The other e-HRM module is the Bamboo HR system. It is a cloud-based HR system for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). It offers SMEs and startups a human resources information system (HRIS), including an applicant tracking system and tools for managing all aspects of the employee lifecycle. It also offers automation tools for HR processes, and is available in multiple languages and currencies. This system allows HR professionals and managers to track organizational data such as employee turnover and retention rates. It also offers customization services, multiple accounts for administrators, technical support for users, and the ability to manage inactive employees (Halim & Rosli, 2018).

While HRM systems are numerous, they are not limited to managing administrative processes. Rather, they are strategic tools that contribute to achieving the strategic objectives of the organisation in terms of quality, efficiency, effectiveness, and investment and development of human resources. However, the Palestinian reality, particularly in Gaza, highlights the need for these systems to achieve a different strategic objective. The sector is facing significant challenges due to the ongoing war and deteriorating infrastructure, which has directly impacted the education sector. Therefore, the importance of HRM systems is not limited to supporting traditional administrative aspects. Rather, they have become essential to ensuring the continuity of educational services. This is achieved by improving the management of educational and administrative staff despite frequent power outages and poor communications. They also facilitate access to employee data, organise schedules, and monitor actual performance remotely. They also support emergency plans and rapid response during crises.

2.6 Impact of Wars on E-HRM

Wars and crises to similar to the genocide in Gaza create a major impact on the possibility of e-HRM and impose significant challenges on organisations or might force them to

adapt to changing circumstances, Iriqat et al. (2025). Examples of transformations that organisations are forced to make to their structure or operations include:

2.6.1 Rapid Digital Transformation

In times of war and crises, electronic systems become even more important to maintain business continuity. The organisations would think about how to manage their HRM systems and their employees remotely. This means that the organisation would use more cloud solutions to store and secure data access at any time. Virtual communication tools such as Zoom and Microsoft Teams would be used more to ensure effective communication between teams.

2.6.2 Manage More Data Security Challenges

With increased reliance on e-systems, the risk of cyberattacks increases. This requires organisations to strengthen protection systems and secure employee data. This means the organisation need to train teams on cybersecurity to reduce breaches. This might require more investment in encryption and backup solutions.

2.6.3 Remote Work Management

Wars and crises force many organisations to implement remote work models, which impacts monitoring employee performance using electronic evaluation systems. Providing psychological and social support to employees to cope with the stress of crises. Amending policies to include greater flexibility in working hours and tasks.

2.6.4 Talent Recruitment and Workforce Management

In some cases, organisations are forced to redeploy employees due to shifting priorities, including focusing on e-recruitment to quickly fill job gaps, using artificial intelligence to analyse data and make effective hiring decisions. The crisis would help to restructure policies and adapt to changing circumstances, including reviewing employment contracts and wage policies are being reviewed due to the economic conditions resulting from wars and crises, relying on automation technologies to reduce costs and increase efficiency, and launching psychological and professional support programs to help employees adapt.

2.7 How e-HRM technologies Overcome Unprecedented Challenges of Wars?

Wars and crises pose unprecedented challenges, but technology helps adapt and reposition to ensure business continuity. Many of the challenges that accompany the transition from traditional business models to technological ones also arise, including cybersecurity and risk management, which are essential to protecting businesses. Institutions need to continually update their policies to ensure continuity.

In this context, global challenges have recently imposed themselves in the field of entrepreneurship and institutional work on many international and local institutions. These challenges have manifested in the need to shift to electronic work during the global pandemic (COVID-19). This pandemic has forced many institutions to adopt electronic

models to ensure continuity. Among the local institutions that have been able to adapt and transition is the Islamic University of Gaza (IUG). This experience in performance has given the university the opportunity to continue adopting these electronic models during the numerous wars that Gaza has experienced, especially the October 7, 2023 war, which was considered the fundamental foundation for continuing the educational process. Buheji (2025b), Migdad et al. (2024b).

The world has recently witnessed rapid and radical developments. Organisations have found themselves facing major changes and must address these challenges by offering new and better solutions. Consequently, administrations have begun to compete in utilising the latest innovations in the administrative field to shift from traditional performance to a modern one. Information technology systems have become an integral part of their strategy to achieve their goals by improving productivity, disseminating knowledge, and supporting the creative capabilities of their employees. They have created new practices and made changes to their functions, even infecting the HRM, considering it the primary resource upon which future development depends.

This has led to the emergence of e-HRM as a modern model that helps the conscious use of information and communications technologies, implementing effective and responsive activities, enabling them to create a competitive advantage (Boussah and Boussoussa 2023). Implementing e-HRM during wars poses a significant challenge for organisations, especially with the total disruption or destruction of the technical infrastructure. Wars can destroy communication networks and the internet, hindering the operation of electronic human resources systems.

In times of insecurity similar to the one in the War on Gaza, organisations are more vulnerable to cyber-attacks, and employee data or electronic systems can be targeted. Wars can lead to the displacement or loss of employees, including human resources specialists and technicians responsible for operating electronic systems, creating a gap in the required skills. Economic impacts can lead to the disruption of the financial and banking system, which in turn can lead to delayed salary payments or complicate electronic transfers, especially in light of economic sanctions or currency collapse. There are many obstacles, and we will suffice with what has been mentioned (Jabbara, 2023). The above demonstrates that digital transformation in e-HRM is not simply an option today, but rather a necessity imposed by current circumstances and challenges. However, its implementation requires a relatively stable environment and a secure infrastructure that is protected from threats. Therefore, organisations must incorporate emergency scenarios and crisis response into their strategic plans to ensure the continuity of operations based on electronic systems, even under exceptional and less-than-ideal circumstances.

3.0 Methodology

Given the research focus on how to optimise the use of e-HRM to sustain higher education operations during war, the methodology combined both qualitative and case-study approaches with practical insights from crisis management. The study adopts a qualitative case study approach, focusing on the Islamic University of Gaza (IUG) as a critical case due to its resilience during wartime.

The research design includes an exploratory analysis of e-HRM's role in crisis management. A comparative analysis of war-impacted universities in different countries is identified to retrieve best practices. Then, a practical assessment of IUG's e-HRM adaptations during the 2023-24 war is presented as a case study.

Given the war conditions, the data is gathered through semi-structured interviews with IUG faculty, HR managers, and IT staff (conducted remotely if possible). The authors also used university reports, policy documents, and internal communications from IUG. The academic literature on e-HRM in conflict zones was reviewed along with the media reports, which provided further assessments on Gaza's higher education sector.

4.0 Application to the Islamic University in Gaza

The Islamic University of Gaza (IUG) enjoys an excellent academic reputation locally and internationally. Over the past four decades, it has established academic relationships with numerous universities and organisations around the world to conduct joint research, organise conferences, and facilitate faculty and student exchanges. Tens of thousands of graduates from the university work in diverse fields, many of whom hold senior positions in local and international institutions.

IUG comprises eleven colleges, and before the start of the current Israeli war, the student body numbered approximately 17,000, 63% of whom were female. The university provides a distinguished academic environment, utilising various technologies (such as computer labs, e-learning through Moodle, and video conferencing), along with other high-quality facilities (such as libraries, gardens, gymnasiums, and playgrounds).

Students with physical, visual, and hearing disabilities have received scholarships and are assisted by a special needs office (Al-Nabiah, 2024). Regarding the research topic of implementing e-HRM in higher education institutions, particularly the IUG, this topic faces significant challenges, especially in light of the current wartime conditions. These challenges impact e-HRM policies and practices in multiple ways, the most prominent of which, according to observations, are: (IUG Website, 2024).

The recent war in Gaza led to the destruction of most of the IUG infrastructure for many aspects of life, including, of course, communications networks and the internet. This impacted the performance of IUG. In addition, the war created challenges related to

communication and coordination among IUG employees, both with each other and with management, which are also present due to the interruption of electronic services.

In addition to the psychological and social impacts on employees, the war affected the IUG employees' desire to interact with e-HRM, and this even increased with the restrictions or lack of resources. Despite these challenges, educational institutions such as the IUG adapted to difficult circumstances and managed to ensure the continuity of its HRM operations.

Many universities have resumed their education online, ensuring that those who can continue their studies do not miss the academic year. Liaison offices have been established in neighbouring countries to monitor the educational process. For example, Dr Migadad, one of the co-authors of this paper, a professor at IUG, has continued teaching doctoral students in management, economics, and accounting. However, academics and students alike face numerous challenges in the educational process, most notably the availability of the internet, psychological and security instability, and the continued indiscriminate bombing. Therefore, international institutions need to play a role in facilitating the educational process by providing internet-related services and relevant programs to ensure the continuity of education.

IUG continues to make efforts that focus on alternative technologies, such as wireless networks, to ensure continuity of its communication with its students and HRM. The university secured data, implemented advanced security protocols, and maintained backup copies of data in secure locations. IUG adopted flexible policies that allow remote work and the use of alternative electronic platforms as needed.

5.0 Discussion and Conclusion

The war on Gaza has presented unprecedented challenges to higher education institutions, testing their ability to sustain operations amid widespread destruction and disruption. This study highlights what type of e-HRM is needed to serve as a lifeline for universities under fire, taking the experience of the Islamic University of Gaza (IUG).

The authors focused on the continuity of faculty work from remote spaces, while still collaborating to maintain the flow of education and research despite severe infrastructure limitations. The implication of this study focus on how to build more strategic e-HRM plan that can mitigate some of the most crippling effects of war on academic institutions.

Comparative lessons from other conflict zones suggest that long-term resilience depends mainly on three factors. The most important factor is the investment in war-resistant digital infrastructure. Then, the integration of mental health and crisis management into HR policies.

The case of IUG underscores a broader imperative: e-HRM is no longer optional for institutions in crisis zones but a necessity for survival. Future research should explore scalable models for resource-constrained environments and the ethical dimensions of digital reliance in warfare. For now, this study serves as both a warning and a roadmap, highlighting the fragility of education under siege while offering actionable strategies to uphold it.

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